

	Artificial diet	Tobacco	Devil's claw
4th instar			
Feeding switch rate	10.25(7.48, 18.24)	16.21(11.72, 30.84)	56.22(36.33, 147.69)
Non-feeding switch rate	4.93(3, 10.19)	10.19(7.32, 19.52)	24.36(16.85, 57.95)
5th instar			
Feeding switch rate	16.85(12.59, 29.53)	10.7(6.2, 42.61)	59.43(40.81, 187.89)
Non-feeding switch rate	11.05(8.15, 18.91)	12.63(8, 46.23)	37.99(25.23, 128.16)